

Multi-functional Reversible Gate for Programmable Silicon Photonics

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Abstract—Reversible gates are capable of supporting bidirectional signal flow and find usage in photonic signal processing. In contrast to electronic components, photonic components are bidirectional in nature, where the light signal passes in the forward and feedback manner as well. Reversible gates are isomorphically equivalent to photonic components, since it follows an unitary linear transformation supports a single-input single-output(SISO) and multi-input and multi-output(MIMO). The use of reversible gates facilitates the features namely scalability and modular approach for the programmable photonic integrated circuits. In this work, a new approach called multi-level abstraction for the VLSI-photonic integrated circuits are presented with the help of traditional VLSI-electronic circuits. With this approach we divided the entire process into front-end and back-end, where in the front-end the functional verification using different modeling styles. this multi-level abstraction slowly increases the complexity in the analysis starting from behavioral modeling to empirical modeling. The suitability of the proposed approach is verified with the design of optical beam steering application. The results obtained using the proposed approach shows an accuracy of ?percent similar to traditional EM simulation and greatly reduced the circuit complexity in the overall analysis. The proposed approach acts as a new paradigm and most suitable that the VLSI-electronic IC designers readily adopt and migrate to VLSI photonic IC design. In near future, the EDA companies will adopt the proposed approach, as a token of adoption Lucedo photonics used Verilog-A for photonic component and circuit design. The industrial leader in the photonic IC simulation Lumerical also adopted the Verilog-A for the modeling. The adoption of VLSI-electronic circuit design approach for the design of VLSI-photonic circuits is evident from these major.

Index Terms—Reconfigurable photonics, Quasi-rigorous simulation, VLSI-photonic ICs, mixed-signal flow modeling

I. Introduction

A. Reversible gates

Reversible mechanisms are useful, where the component supports its operation in bidirectional way. Reversible gates are most suitable to mimic the functionality of the photonic components namely directional coupler, MZI and customized photonic switches. The Pauli matrices are used to describe the mechanism behind reversible gates. These reversible gates are capable of making programmable photonic component. A new paradigm using field-programmable photonic array using reversible analog array is first proposed by Jose capmany and the team.

B. Photonic components

In general, EM simulations are employed to verify the functionality of a photonic component. The traditional EM simulation methods namely EIM, BPM, EME and FDTD, TMM are commonly used. For a component design these methods provides better accuracy with much larger execution time. These methods are broadly classified into time and frequency domain analysis. Based on these methods, 2D or 3D modeling and simulation are carried out by photonic component designer by considering the specific constraints such as geometrical parameters, wavelength range of operation, loss and cross-talk levels, etc.

Some method considers only one way of computing, but some tools perform the two way computation since photonic components are inherently bidirectional. The mechanism such as transmission and reflection are always exists together. The complexity of photonic circuits depends in the method to evaluate the functionality and the analysis [1-4]. For larger photonic circuits, the conventional design methods are lagging in terms of execution time, hence an alternative approach is required to perform functional verification of larger and very larger photonic circuits.

In our proposed approach, a quasi-rigorous functional verification of VLSI-photonic circuit can be verified using the hardware design language and empirical modeling. The empirical models are created after designing the physical/device level modeling. Based on the designed geometrical parameter the empirical models for the discrete photonic component is developed. All the required discrete photonic component are designed and stored as its equivalent empirical model. Using the multiple architecture configuration of VHDL, a multiple architecture descriptions are possible. This approach provides a trade-off performances in terms of accuracy and execution.

This approach will be useful at the initial stage of photonic circuit design and verification. in order to get more accurate result a compact model library will be used from the recognized industrial foundry. our approach is a modular, technology independent, it supports all the photonic technology such as InP, SiN, SOI and hybrid platform, since it uses only the compact model provided by the respective foundry [5-7].

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C. Programmable photonics

The programmable photonic creates a new paradigm shift in the conventional photonics. man literature papers discusses the programmable photonic mechanism. The main feature of programmable photonics are the adaptability if various functions in the common photonic platform. The photonic fabrics are configured or programmed through software control. This stage is similar to the steps followed in the traditional FPGA applications. The only one programmable photonic FPGA from iPronecs, te team lead by Jose Capmany is the leader in this area [8-10].

D. Analog signal processing

The EM signals are considered as analog in nature. The lightwave is also regarded as EM wave, and moreover the reversible gate directly accepts analog signals and process. This feature enables the photonic components to process the quantum informations, since it have continuous states of operation. In the special case, the photonic components also support digital signals, which leads to digital photonics. But the drawback in dealing with digital data is the requirement of the very high-speed ADC/DAC which is the bottleneck of digital photonics and the speed of the operation is limited by analog-digital conversion [11-13].

E. VLSI-IC design

in traditional electronic IC design, the standard design flow involves the specification development, architecture design, functional description, RTL description, synthesis, placement and routing, fabrication and testing. Since, the silicon-photonics IC is based on the existing CMOS fabrication, it also follows the same design flow. The only requirement is the process design kit (PDK) similar to the compact model library (CML). In the front-end design flow, only the functionalities are verified and in the back end design the realized hardware component are mapped with the PDK library. This approach creates a ease design compared to EM simulations, where the component designer itself can not decide all the fabrication constraints, these details should be obtained from the foundry. Hence, it is better to divide the design flow into two as available in the electronic IC design namely front-end design and back-end design. This newer approach enables the electronic IC designer to easily adopt the design of photonic IC design [14-16].

F. Process design kit

The process design kit are type of design constraints provided by the respective foundry vendor. The generic photonic component design in the front-end now mapped to PDK, again the functionalities are to be verified. Once, the design meets all the design constraints an equivalent layout will be generated in the standard GDS format. For the fabrication of photonic ICs, the GDS file should be given as in the input file to the foundry for the fabrication [17].

II. Reversible gates

Forward operation of the tunable directional coupler is given by

$$\begin{bmatrix} b1 \\ b2 \end{bmatrix} = -je^{j\Delta\phi} \begin{bmatrix} \sin \theta & \cos \theta \\ \cos \theta & -\sin \theta \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} a1 \\ a2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

Backward operation of the tunable directional coupler is given by

$$\begin{bmatrix} a1 \\ a2 \end{bmatrix} = -je^{j\Delta\phi} \begin{bmatrix} \sin \theta & \cos \theta \\ \cos \theta & -\sin \theta \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} b1 \\ b2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

where the phase factor $\Delta\phi$ and coupling factor κ are externally controlled by means of either acoustic, thermo or electro-optic way. In his work we adopted an electro-optic mechanism to control the κ and phase factor. The equation (1), is used to describe the bar-state, cross-state and variable coupling operations. The bar-state operation is carried out by substituting $\theta=0$ and the cross-state operation is achieved by substituting the $\theta=\pi/2$. For the 3-dB beam splitter/combiner the above equations (1), and (2) are described as follows.

$$\begin{bmatrix} b1 \\ b2 \end{bmatrix} = -je^{j\Delta\phi} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 1 & -1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} a1 \\ a2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

A. Configurable reversible gate (CRG)

The isomorphically equivalent photonic component of the configurable reversible gate is shown in Fig.1, which is commonly referred as tunable directional coupler (TDC). The proper configuration of the directional coupler enable to use as 3-dB beam splitter/combiner, bar-state switch, cross-state switch and variable coupler. The signal in one waveguide is completely transferred to a parallel waveguide after each periodic length L_c by a factor called coupling constant , which depends on the wavelength of operation, the waveguide geometry and the refractive indices of the materials being used [21]. These dependencies result in the TDCs being susceptible to fabrication errors that can change the designed wavelength of operation, bandwidth and uniformity. where both $K = \cos^2\theta$ and Δ_{PPAB} can be changed by means of two external (electronic, mechanic, acoustic) control signals through a linear relationship.

Fig. 1. The graphical representation of the 2x2 reversible gate (a) isomorphically equivalent 2x2 tunable directional coupler (b) symbol

B. 2×2 Mach–Zehnder interferometer

The schematic representation of the 2×2 Mach–Zehnder interferometer is shown in Fig.2. The incoming light launched in the single-mode waveguide is splitted into equal amount by the beam splitter. The equally divided beams then travel through the top and bottom waveguides. At the output, the splitted beams are combined again and based on the phase-difference between the two beams, an interference effect takes place. If the phase-difference between the two waveguide path is zero, then a constructive interference effect takes place. This state of operation is commonly referred to as on-state. For the phase difference of π radians, a destructive interference takes place and the state of operation is known as off-state.

Fig. 2. The schematic representation of the 2×2 Mach-Zehnder interferometer.

C. 2×1 photonic switch

The schematic presentation of the 2×1 MZI switch is shown in Fig.3. The 2×1 MZI switch incorporates two 1×1 MZM in each waveguide section to provide the on-off feature for the respective waveguide branch and to ensure the crosstalk suppression and uses a directional coupler to switch the light to either of the output port. The light propagation is controlled using three electric fields V_{dc} , V_{m1} and V_{m2} respectively in the directional coupler, top and bottom MZMs.

Fig. 3. The schematic representation of the designed 2×1 photonic switch.

The simulated result for the developed empirical model is shown in Fig.???. In the VHDL code, the voltage values are represented with the real data type of range -1.0 to +1.0, hence the required half-wave driving voltage is scaled down to 1.0 to represent 10 V. For the value of $v(t)=0$ V, the light input available at the top-port is available at the

output-port and for $v(t)=10$ V, the light input available at the bottom port is available at the output-port.

D. 1×2 photonic switch

The schematic representation of the 1×2 MZI crossbar photonic switch is shown in Fig.4 in which, the light launched at the input port is either propagated to the bar output port or to the cross-output port. In the absence of electric field and with the suitable coupling distance, the directional coupler allows the incoming light to the cross-port output. In order to change the direction of propagation from cross-port to bar-port an external driving voltage (V_{dc}) of 10 V is applied to the directional coupler. The 1×1 MZM is used to control the flow of light in each waveguide path being propagated to output using V_{m1} and V_{m2} driving voltages. This feature is useful to selectively block the light propagation in the corresponding waveguide path.

Fig. 4. The schematic representation of the 1×2 photonic switch.

The simulated result for the developed empirical model for the 1×2 photonic switch is shown in Fig.???. In the VHDL code, the voltage values are represented with the real data type of range -1.0 to +1.0, hence the required half-wave driving voltage is scaled down to 1.0 to represent 10 V. For the value of $v(t)=0$ V, the input light is available at the bottom output-port and for $v(t)=10$ V, the input light is available at the top output-port.

III. Programmable photonics

In our analysis, all the required photonic components are first designed using the FD-BPM technique. The transmission characteristics of the designed photonic components are converted into an empirical model using least-square error method [22]. The empirical model is then coded using VHDL as a separate empirical abstraction level architecture in addition to the behavioral abstraction. This feature enable the designer to switch the type of architecture at anytime using VHDL's architecture configuration option. The propagation loss and the loss due to the waveguide crossings are not considered to show the impact of the designed photonic components performance using the proposed approach with empirical abstraction level. The insertion-losses associated with the individual integrated photonic component are incorporated in the

respective empirical models. The $N \times N$ dilated-banyan switch fabric consists of a $2N(N-1)$ number of switches, which is similar to switch counts available in switch-and-select architecture [23]. The 4×4 dilated-banyan switch fabrics (DBSF) are considered for the feasibility verification of the proposed approach. The 4×4 dilated-banyan

Fig. 5. The architecture of the dilated-banyan switch fabrics.

switch fabrics consist of 4- stages, such as input-stage, output-stage, two middle-stages that connect input-stages and output-stages as described in Fig.5. Our contribution to the analysis of DBSF is to use the developed empirical models for 1×2 and 2×1 crossbar photonic switch functionalities. The configurations of different switches in the 4×4 switch fabrics are controlled using the configuration matrix as shown in Fig.6. The simulated results for the default configurations ($E_{in1} \rightarrow E_{out1}$, $E_{in2} \rightarrow E_{out2}$, $E_{in3} \rightarrow E_{out3}$ and $E_{in4} \rightarrow E_{out4}$) is shown in Fig.??.

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--Configuration bits
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type stg1_sw_matrix is array(0 to 3, 0 to 3) of std_logic;
signal stg1_config_bits:stg1_sw_matrix:=("0xxx", "x0xx", "xx0x", "xxxx0");

type stg2_sw_matrix is array(0 to 7, 0 to 3) of std_logic;
signal stg2_config_bits:stg2_sw_matrix:=("0xxx", "x0xx", "xx0x", "xxxx0",
"xxxx", "xxxx", "xxxx", "xxxx");

type stg3_sw_matrix is array(0 to 7, 0 to 3) of std_logic;
signal stg3_config_bits:stg3_sw_matrix:=("1xxx", "x1xx", "xx1x", "xxx1",
"xxxx", "xxxx", "xxxx", "xxxx");

type stg4_sw_matrix is array(0 to 3, 0 to 3) of std_logic;
signal stg4_config_bits:stg4_sw_matrix:=("1xxx", "x1xx", "xx1x", "xxx1");
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Fig. 6. Setting up the configuration of individual photonic component in the SDM switch fabrics.

to the symmetric nature of dilated-banyan switch fabrics, all the light paths in the switch fabrics offer a uniform propagation loss. The designed 1×2 and 2×1 crossbar photonic switches show a different transmission levels for the bar-state and the cross-state operation. The light takes different bar-state and cross-state while propagating through the entire switch fabrics. Depending upon the number of bar-state and cross-state it passes leads to a different amount of transmission losses in each path.

TABLE I
Simulated transmission levels of the 4×4 dilated-banyan switch fabrics

Stage-1	Stage-2	Stage-3	Stage-4
1×2 switches		2×1 switches	
$E_{i1} \rightarrow E_{o2}$	$E_{i2} \rightarrow E_{o4}$	$E_{i3} \rightarrow E_{o3}$	$E_{i4} \rightarrow E_{o1}$
-0.1938	-0.3704	-0.6936	-0.7306
-0.1769	-0.3704	-0.6936	-0.7306
-0.1938	-0.3704	-0.4075	-0.7306
-0.1769	-0.3704	-0.4075	-0.7306

Any customized configuration is possible by setting up each 1×2 or 2×1 photonic switches either in bar- or cross-state. The operational principle of the considered 4×4 dilated-banyan switch fabrics is as follows. For an arbitrary configuration map the input-output is related using a generic relationship, namely $I_m \rightarrow O_n$. The variable I and O represents the input and output light intensity respectively. The subscripts m and n represents input and output ports of the switch fabric and takes values from 1 to 4 for $N = 4$. Due to the symmetric nature of DBSF architecture, all the light paths in the switch fabrics offer a uniform insertion loss. According to the required configuration map, the designed switch fabrics can be programmed through the software control. The designed 1×2 and 2×1 MZI crossbar photonic switches show a different transmission levels for the bar-state and the cross-state operation. The light takes different bar-state and cross-state while propagating through the entire switch fabrics. Depending upon the specific configuration map, each light path shows a different insertion losses and crosstalk level. Due to different transmission loss in the 1×2 and 2×1 MZI switches, each light path incurs a different transmission loss levels for the specific configuration map considered which is shown in Table I. This transmission level ensures how each photonic switch reduces the crosstalk in each stage of the light path. To configure the required light path, the corresponding input 1×2 MZI photonic switch and successor switches are configured to be in the ON-state in order to establish the intended propagation path and the unused switches are maintained in the OFF-state.

IV. Conclusion

The very large scale integrated photonic component needs a simple yet a quasi-rigorous simulation approach. In this article, we presented a simple quasi-rigorous modular mixed-signal flow modeling technique for analyzing the VLSI-photonic circuits. The developed empirical models represented the quasi-rigorous model of the integrated photonic components. The proposed approach is a modular, scalable, parameterizable and follows signal flow mechanism suitable for modeling the VLSI-photonic circuits. The proposed approach greatly reduces the computational complexity, supports denser integration of photonic components and quasi-rigorous analysis for the VLSI-photonic circuits.

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